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The historical surface ruptures in the Laguna Salada Fault region - Baja California, Mexico

1 Introduction

Before the 2016 December meetings (FDHA workshop, 8-9th December, and AGU Fall Meeting, 11-16th December) in the Bay Area of Northern California, we spent two days with Martin Siem (), guided by Tom Rockwell (University of San Diego) in the Laguna Salada Desert (Baja California, Mexico).

The objective was to observe the surface ruptures (1892, 1934, 2010) associated with historical earthquakes that occurred along the Laguna Salada shoreline in the Cucapah range. The most recent surface rupture has been extensively studied by several authors and the accurate data have been published recently, so that this case will be included in the SURE database.

2 Geological background

In this high-strain region between Pacific and North-American plates, the Laguna Salada Fault is the southern continuation of the strike-slip Elsinore Fault Zone into the Extensional Baja California Province. It is an oblique transtensional fault, which is the main fault bounding the Laguna Salada basin to the north-east.

Figure 1: Location of the Laguna Salada fault zone, few tens km west of the plate boundary (red line) between Pacific plate (to the west) and North American plate (to the east). The relative right-lateral displacement is accommodated along the NW-SE plate boundary, at around 30 mm/y

The Laguna Salada (LSF) is a west-dipping high-angle fault which ruptured up to the ground surface in 1892 during a M7+ earthquake (Figure 2). To the south, the LSF cross-cuts a low-angle west dipping fault (Cañada David Detachment, CDD), which ruptured to the surface in 1934 during a M6.5 earthquake. Finally, the M7.2 El Mayor-Cucapah (EMC) earthquake caused the rupture of various segments in the ranges (Fletcher et al., 2014), linked at depth to a low-angle structure (Fletcher et al., 2016).

Figure 2 : Map of the 2010 rupture during the M7.2 El Mayor-Cucapah (EMC) earthquake. Note the location of the 1934 and 1892 epicenters at the NE margin of the Laguna Salada basin. CDD is the Cañada David Detachment fault. The plate boundary between Pacific and North-American Plates corresponds to the Imperial and Cerro Prieto faults, east of the visited sites (Figure from Fletcher et al., 2014).

The Laguna Salada Basin is a thick half-graben tectonically bounded to the NE (LSF and CDD faults), with up to 4 km post-Miocene sedimentary fill (Fletcher and Spelz, 2009). Until the end of the 1980's, the Laguna Salada was a lake.

3 M7.2 2010 El Mayor-Cucapah earthquake surface rupture

The most recent event, which occurred in 2010, is known as the M7.2 El Mayor-Cucapah (EMC) earthquake. It created, north of its epicenter, a 55 km long rupture across the El Mayor and Cucapah mountain ranges, partly on previously unknown fault strands. South of the epicenter, the fault remained blind over ~50 km. The first two pictures below depict the rupture on the Paso Superior and Borrego Segments (Fletcher et al., 2014), respectively.

Figure 3 : The Laguna Salada Fault (in the background) bounds to the north-east the thick half-graben infill. The flat surface corresponds to a recent lacustrine aggradation surface

Figure 4 : Top - the Laguna Salada was a lake until the 1980's. Bottom - Overview of the landscape (Cucapah range and Laguna Salada) and the 2010 earthquake surface rupture; to the left, location of observed sites on the Borrego segment (view towards the SE).

Figure 5 : View to the north of the 2010 rupture on the Paso Superior segment, in the northern part of the EMC rupture. This can be seen from the old road running along the Highway 2 between Mexicali-Tijuana.

Figure 6 : View to the north of the 2010 ruptured Borrego segment (see trench dug few months after the quake). Tom Rockwell and colleagues dug many trenches along the 2010 scarp and they could confirm that previous event(s) ruptured the surface at the same place.

Below, the picture shows a typical piercing point that is used to estimate in the field coseismic offset: here around 4 meters in a right-lateral sense and around 1.5-2 meters (SW block uplifted) (Figure 7).

The surface rupture dammed the drainage network for a while, creating a pond where fine sediments (beneath the Oona's and Tom's steps) accumulated during the later flooding events (Figure 8). These last mobilized - during the days/weeks/months after the quake - the dust that has been blown off from the soil during shaking: the fine-grained caps are earthquake event layers.

Interestingly, the 2010 EMC earthquake triggered many "distributed" deformation such as secondary scarps on regional active faults. Figure 9 shows an example of reactivation of the SW-dipping Laguna Salada fault, close to the Highway 2.

Figure 7 : 2010 oblique slip on the Borrego segment. The 2 geologists in the background stand on the initially same morphological feature, illustrating the dextro-normal sense of slip during the quake

Figure 8 : Along the Borrego segment, the drainage network has been dammed and dust clouds' material blown off during shaking has been eventually deposited in the ponds

Figure 9 : Small displacement distributed along the Laguna Salada segment, close to Highway 2.

4 The M7+ 1892 Laguna Salada earthquake surface rupture

Another stunning geological feature of the area is the Laguna Salada fault and its 1892 earthquake surface rupture (Mueller and Rockwell, 1995). According to the recent assessment by Rockwell et al. (2015), the earthquake magnitude is in the same range as the 2010 EMC event, and the revised rupture length is around 58 km. Kinematics of the earthquake mostly led to oblique slip (dextro-normal) along the NW fault.

Figure 10 illustrates the nice preservation of the 1892 scarp which has completely disrupted the valley floor, creating a small "perched canyon".

Figure 10 : the 1892 Laguna Salada earthquake scarp is well preserved in the landscape. It is marked by a typical greenish tone and its preservation leaves visible perched canyons and displaced active screes.

To the south of the rupture (Cañon Rojo), the change in strike is responsible for a pure dip-slip displacement during the 1892 quake: this caused this fresh and 5-m high free-face dipping $\sim 50^\circ$ to the W-NW (Figure 11).

The fault zone that ruptured in 1892 is a long-lived structure. The long-term history of this fault is obvious when staring at the large gouge, with cataclasite/mylonite and even pseudo-tachylite that injects into small fractures of the gouge (Figure 12). These pseudo-tachylite are a marker of partial melting at crustal depths due to coseismic friction in the fault gouge. The whole fault zone is underlined in the landscape by its greenish colour due to metamorphic chlorite.

Figure 11 : Two views of the same 1892 scarp at Canyon Rojo, in the southernmost part of the rupture. The change in strike, visible on the right picture, causes the pure dip-slip movement on the free-face close to the geologist (Tom). The picture on the left illustrates the amount of slip during the single event.

Figure 12 : Zoom in on the fault gouge zone, with injected pseudo-tachylite in the greenish (chlorite) cataclasite/mylonite

During its "recent" history, the fault underwent several morphogenic (with surface rupture) earthquakes that successively displaced the alluvial deposits. The cumulative scarp is around 5 m high (Figure 13) and displaces successive Holocene alluvial fans organized in tectonic terraces on the (uplifted) footwall.

After a recent revision, Rockwell et al (2015) proposed a new segmentation, based on image analysis and field mapping (Figure 14). In some places, we could observe small free-faces corresponding to 2010 reactivation of the 1892 fault scarp (Figure 15).

Figure 13: The fault scarp (blue arrows) in the foreground provides a (minimum) overlook of the Holocene slip cumulated during successive surface rupturing events. These are evidenced by the successive and entrenched terraces in the foot wall (not visible on the picture)

Figure 7. Map of strands that likely ruptured in the 1892 earthquake (bolded thick faults). Observations south of the border are from this study, with additional observations from the Yuha Desert north of the border from S. Isaac (unpublished thesis, 1987). Other strands may also have been involved in 1892 but no longer have sufficient expression to be recognized as a young rupture. Locations of Figure 3 panels are indicated (see GoogleEarth KML file, available in the electronic supplement to this article). The color version of this figure is available only in the electronic edition.

Figure 14 : Surface rupture (red lines) associated with the 1892 earthquake, after Rockwell et al. 2015. (Photograph in Figure 11 was taken at the same location as Fig. 3d, where the fault trace makes a right angle)

Figure 15 : An example of reactivation of 1892 earthquake scarp during the 2010 earthquake, evidenced by the brownish fringe (~20 cm) at the bottom of the ~2 m grey scarp

Figure 17 : View of the 1934 earthquake scarp (blue arrows) vertically displacing the modern alluvial channel. Tom Rockwell and John Fletcher opened the trench several weeks before our visit.

Figure 18 : Tom Rockwell is standing on the edge of a small displaced channel (footwall) and Oona is in the axis of the same channel edge on the hanging wall, highlighting the dextral motion.

Figure 19 : The shallow dip detachment fault which ruptured in 1934 separates the greenish bedrock and the overlying Quaternary alluvial sediments

6 The 2010 El Mayor Cucapah surface rupture with respect to the Petersen et al. (2011) prediction equation

The surface rupture data have been published in two major publications (Fletcher et al., 2014 and Teran et al., 2015) and we could already start to analyze them briefly. For instance, we plotted the values of “secondary displacement” measured and reported by Fletcher et al. (2014), together with the measurements made along the remote faults in American California at large distances (Rymer et al., 2011). On Figure 20, we compare the Fletcher and Rymer values to the predictive regression of Petersen et al. (2011) for a $M7.2$ strike-slip event, which is calibrated for $R < 2$ km or $(\ln R < 7.5)$. Like in the Napa case (Baize and Scotti, 2016), we conclude that the mean value of “secondary displacement” observations (in the red square, below $\ln R = 7.5$) is significantly higher than the predicted mean value, suggested that these predictions need to be updated. It seems that remote slip values (out of the red square) fall well below the prediction. These remote slip evidences are usually qualified as “triggered” displacement clues because not related to the earthquake source.

Figure 20 : Plot of the surface displacement data associated with the 2010 El Mayor-Cucapah, in comparison with the predictive regression (central line: mean value; top and bottom lines: $+\sigma$ and $-\sigma$, respectively) published by Petersen et al. (2011) for strike-slip earthquake faults: $\ln(d)=1.4016*Mw-0.1671*\ln(R)-6.7991$

7 Conclusions

The first aim of the visit was to check in the field the surface ruptures associated with the 2010 M7.2 El Mayor-Cucapah earthquake. We could check the main rupture and several secondary faulting evidences at short distances, up to several hundred meters.

The active faults of the Laguna Salada area actually ruptured three times in more than a century, during M6.5+ earthquakes, despite their relative moderate slip rates (max 3 mm/y, Laguna Salada fault). From this statement and according to the wealth of available works (e.g. Fletcher et al., 2016), it can be concluded that the active faults cannot be considered alone in any hazard assessment, but they “talk to each other”.

Evidences of surface ruptures are exceptionally well preserved in the arid environment. However, the rare extreme climatic events (ex. the last 2013 storm) that hit the area since 1892 significantly damaged the scarps, according to T. Rockwell and the scarps may be degraded even in an arid environment if such climatic events repeat often.

The 1934 earthquake rupture, under study by the US-Mexican team, could be an interesting case to consider in the future database of surface ruptures. Many distributed ruptures have already been mapped at large distances on the detachment hanging wall, in relation with the specific structural context. Moreover, the date of the event make possible that pre- and post-aerial pictures could have been shot above the rupture. We already had a contact with Pierre Lacan (UNAM, Queretaro, Mex), involved in the US-Mex project, to prospect in the Mexican archives for such images. They could be used in the current project with IPGP that use optical correlation techniques (MicMac) to retrieve co-seismic deformations.

8 References

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